

New Records of Marine Fishes from the Puerto Rican Plateau

GEORGE D. DENNIS¹, DANNIE HENSLEY², PATRICK L. COLIN³, AND JOSEPH J. KIMMEL⁴

¹Caribbean Marine Research Center 805 East 46th Place Vero Beach, FL 32963

Current Address: US Fish & Wildlife Service, South Florida Ecological Services Office, 1339 20th Str., Vero Beach, FL 32960, george_dennis@fws.gov

²Department of Marine Sciences University of Puerto Rico Mayagüez, PR 00681-5000

³Coral Reef Research Foundation P.O. Box 1765 Koror, Palau 96940

⁴National Marine Fisheries Service Southeast Regional Office 9721 Executive Center Dr. N. St. Petersburg, FL 33702

ABSTRACT.—Forty-six new records of marine fishes to the Puerto Rican Plateau are reported here with notes on their habitat and life history. The lack of previous reports of many of these species is due to three main reasons: poorly sampled habitats, improved taxonomy, and being a part of a waif fauna. Twenty-one taxa are reported from previously inadequately sampled deep water (>20 m) habitats. Twelve additional species are reported from shallow water in poorly sampled habitats, such as mangroves, soft bottom, or rocky shores. Revision in taxonomy and careful examination revealed seven taxa that are taxonomically distinct from forms previously reported from the area. Finally six rare forms may comprise a waif fauna that infrequently colonizes the region.

KEYWORDS.—ichthyofauna, waif fauna, reef fauna, biogeography

INTRODUCTION

The Puerto Rican Plateau is the easternmost extension of the Greater Antilles composed of eight major islands, Puerto Rico, Vieques, Culebra, St. Thomas, St. John, Tortola, Virgin Gorda, and Anegada (Figure 1). In addition to the major islands, there are numerous islets and cays. This shallow-water bank forms a single biogeographical unit as no land mass is separated by waters deeper than 20 m. The Puerto Rican Plateau differs most from the remaining Greater Antilles by the lack of primary freshwater fishes, i.e., those strictly confined to freshwater (Myers 1938). This indicates that there is a zoogeographical barrier between Hispaniola and Puerto Rico. We did not include islands of the Mona Passage (Mona, Monito, and Desecheo) that will be treated in a separate publication, nor St. Croix that is separated from the Puerto Rican Plateau by at least 2700 m water depth. Numerous scientific studies of fishes were carried out in the region, yet there has not been a summary of new records in the primary literature since Erdman (1956) reported on 108 species. In this span of time many unique

habitats have been explored and sampled. We report on 46 species new to these waters with notes on their habitat and life history.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Records reported include information from field notes, personal observations, and collected specimens. Material in the fish collections of the University of Puerto Rico [UPRM], Academy of Natural Sciences Philadelphia [ANSP] and University of Miami [UMML] were searched for records. UMML specimens are now housed at the Florida Natural History Museum and are listed by their new UF catalog number (UF numbers equal UMML numbers plus 200000, e.g., UMML 1111 = UF 201111). Information on specimens examined is listed in the following order: catalog number, number of specimens: size range (in parentheses), collection method, depth of collection, habitat, location, collector, and date. Lengths are in millimeters; standard length unless otherwise noted as FL (fork length) or TL (total length). Where information is

FIG. 1. Map of the Puerto Rico Plateau with 200 m isobath.

attributable to an author it is noted with the author's initials in parentheses. We follow Eschmeyer et al. (1998) for nomenclature and authorities. Museum catalog codes follow Leviton et al. (1985). We searched other museum collections primarily via the NEODAT database (www.neodat.org) for information on the distribution of rare taxa. These records were not substantiated, but referred to in the distributional account.

SPECIES ACCOUNTS

CLUPEIDAE

Sardinella janeiro (Eigenmann 1894)
orangespot sardine

UPRM 2154 (2: 69-80), trawl, 18 m, off Añasco, Puerto Rico, JE Randall, 7 Aug 64; UPRM 2598 (5: 45-74), trawl, Bahía Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, JE Randall, 5 Jun 1965; UPRM 3376 (1: 73), trawl, Mani Beach near Río Añasco mouth, Puerto Rico, JE Ramsey, 1 Apr 1971.

The long used name *Sardinella brasiliensis* (Steindachner) for the orangespot sardine is preoccupied and the next available name is *S. janeiro* (Eschmeyer et al. 1998). This species is purported to occur throughout the Caribbean sympatrically with its congener *Sardinella aurita* Valenciennes in Cuvier & Valenciennes, but may not be separable from that species (Whitehead 1985). There are sporadic reports of *S. aurita* from Puerto Rican waters (Dennis 2000), but it is not

reported as part of the baitfish fishery (Kimmel 1991). All specimens in the UPRM collection had lower-limb gill rakers of the second and third gill arches lying more or less flat, characteristic of *S. janeiro*. Cervigón (1991) could not identify more than one species with certainty in Venezuela and the same is true here. Neither form appears to be common on the Puerto Rican Plateau.

ENGRAULIDAE

Anchoa cayorum (Fowler 1906)
key anchovy

UPRM 3554 (1: 63), seine, 1 m, Bahía Jobos, Puerto Rico, Piastro & Robinson, 29 Nov 1973.

One specimen of this anchovy was found in UPRM when G. Nelson (AMNH) examined the engraulids. Originally described from the Florida Keys, it is now known from Cuba, Yucatán, Belize (Hildebrand 1963), and Venezuela (Cervigón 1991). It is the only long anal-fin base (more than 25 anal-fin rays) species known from the Caribbean and appears to be uncommon throughout its range (Daly 1970). It should be looked for in collections of *Anchoa parva* (Meek & Hildebrand), a common anchovy that it superficially resembles.

OPHIDIIDAE

C. R. Robins (pers. comm., University of Kansas) along with R. Lea (California

Game & Fish) and K. Moots (Division of Fish & Wildlife, Saipan), is preparing a systematic review of *Lepophidium* and *Ophidion* and kindly provided information on the specimens below and confirmed their identification.

Lepophidium pheromystax Robins 1960
 epsilon cusk-eel

UF 207042, FMNH 69301 (2: 130-175), trawl, 70 m, north coast off Arecibo, Puerto Rico, OREGON Stat. 2667 (18° 31'N, 66° 47'W), 8 Oct 1959; FMNH 65952 (2: 155-156), trawl, 77 m, north of St. Thomas, OREGON Stat. 2607 (18° 35'N, 65° 03'W), 26 Sep 1959.

A southern species ranging from Colombia to Brazil (Robins 1960), it is found off Colombia (Palacio, 1974) and Venezuela (Cervigón 1991) on soft bottom. These specimens are the only records from Caribbean islands we could find.

Ophidion holbrookii (Putnam 1874)
 bank cusk-eel

UF 209081 (1: 90), rotenone, 2 m, Lesser Lameshur Bay, St. John, Randall et al., 6 Jun 1961; UF 221855 (1: 155), trawl, 49 m, Bahía Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, OREGON Stat. 5458 (18° 6.5'N, 67° 23'W), 3 Jun 1965.

Described from off Key West, Florida and reported south to Brazil (Robins and Ray 1986), it is found on soft bottom in the eastern Gulf of Mexico (Darovec 1995) and off Venezuela (Cervigón 1991). The bank cusk-eel is typically found deeper than 18 m making the shallow-water record from St. John unusual. Museum database records indicate a continental distribution with the only other island records from the Bahamas and Cuba.

Ophidion lagochila (Böhlke & Robins 1959)
 harelip cusk-eel

ANSP 142863 [formerly UPRM 2236] (1: 63), rotenone, El Negro reef, 12 m, Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, JE Randall, 8 Apr 1963.

Cohen and Nielsen (1978) reassigned this species from *Parophidion* to *Ophidion* due to lack of scales on top and sides of head. Previously known only from off New Providence, Bahamas on sandy bottom near

reefs (Böhlke and Robins 1959) and Bermuda (Smith-Vaniz et al. 1999); it was collected in a similar habitat at El Negro reef off Mayagüez, Puerto Rico. There are museum database records from Anguilla and Tobago. Also it is reported from Monito in the Mona Passage (Dennis unpublished data).

Ophidion nocomis Robins & Böhlke 1959
 letter opener

UPRM 2691 (1: 86), rotenone, sandy bottom, 12 m, Crashboat Basin, Aguadilla, Puerto Rico, Randall & Ramsey, 11 Nov 1965; UF 218229 (4: 63-77 mm TL), rotenone, 22 m, Crashboat Basin, Aguadilla, Puerto Rico, Randall & Cooke, 24 Jul 1965; ANSP 142868 [same lot as UF 218229, formerly UPRM 2669] (1: 70), rotenone, 22 m, sand with *Halophila*, Crashboat Basin, Aguadilla, Puerto Rico, JE Randall, 24 Jul 1965.

Previously known only from the type series from the Bahamas (Robins and Böhlke 1959), where it was collected on shallow sandy bottom. It is found here deeper on the same bottom type. There are also museum records from Tobago and Barbados.

BYTHITIDAE

Stygnobrotula latebricola Böhlke 1957
 black widow

ANSP 144695 (2: 92-104 mm TL), hand, 109 m, shelf-edge reef, El Buoy, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 13 Aug 1976.

One specimen died on the surface and the larger specimen was kept in aquarium for several months (PLC). The black widow is a rare reef-dwelling species known from off West Palm Beach (Humann 1994), Florida Keys (Starck 1968), Bahamas (Böhlke and Chaplin 1968), St. Croix (Clavijo et al. 1980), Colombia (Garzón and Acero 1983), Venezuela (Cervigón 1991), and Curaçao.

EXOCOETIDAE

Cheilopogon cyanopterus (Valenciennes
 in Cuvier & Valenciennes 1846)
 margined flyingfish

UPRM 3503 (1: 272), off La Parguera; UPRM 1746 (1: 202), off La Parguera.

This species is commonly found near oceanic islands with records throughout the Caribbean (Parin and Belyanina 1996). The flyingfishes from the Puerto Rican Plateau are poorly known and this species may have been confused with other *Cheilopogon* species (Dennis 2000).

Exocoetus obtusirostris Günther 1866
oceanic two-wing flyingfish

UPRM 3711 (1: 28), dipped, off La Parguera, Puerto Rico, L Almodovar, 25 Feb 1963; UF 234156 (4: 75-100), cleared and stained, off San Juan, Puerto Rico, deSilva & Erdman, 8 Sep 1962.

A common western Atlantic species, but apparently not ordinarily found near islands of the Puerto Rican Plateau or Lesser Antilles (Bruun 1935, Breder 1938). The juveniles listed here may have been transported near shore from offshore populations in the Caribbean Sea.

Prognichthys occidentalis Parin 1999
bluntnose flyingfish

UPRM 3709 (1: 33), dipped, shelf edge, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, L Almodovar, 6 Nov 1960.

Parin (1999) restricts *Prognichthys gibbifrons* (Valenciennes in Cuvier & Valenciennes) to the eastern Atlantic and named the western Atlantic species *Prognichthys occidentalis*. Breder (1938) indicates several offshore records near Puerto Rico and the Virgin Islands in his Figure 39, but no specimens were listed from the area. Though a neritic species, it is also known only from juveniles in Bermuda (Smith-Vaniz et al. 1999). If common it should have shown up in studies of pelagic fish food habits. It may be part of the waif fauna.

HOLOCENTRIDAE

Corniger spinosus Agassiz in Spix & Agassiz 1831
spinycheek soldierfish

ANSP 144596 (1: 138), trap, 200 m, shelf-edge reef, El Buoy, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 7 Oct 1976.

Reported from South Carolina to Brazil,

but with only one Caribbean record from Cuba (Woods and Sonoda 1973). This cryptic species is found on reefs in deep water. The specimen listed here was maintained alive in aquaria for 12 hours. The spinycheek soldierfish was not reported from previous submersible work in the area (Nelson and Appeldoorn 1985), but may be part of the slope (>200 m) fauna here. Visually it can be confused with the other all-red soldierfish, *Plectrypops retrospinus* (Guichenot), that occurs more frequently throughout the Caribbean, but in shallower water.

Sargocentron poco (Woods 1965)
saddle squirrelfish

ANSP 139255 (1: 72), 30 m, shelf-edge reef, Salinas de Ensenada, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 7 May 1978; ANSP 144383 (1: 102), deep sand channels, 27 m, shelf-edge reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, J. E. Randall, 1 Jun 1976.

The saddle squirrelfish is the least abundant shallow-water species of squirrelfish. It is known from Bermuda (Smith-Vaniz et al. 1999), Bahamas, Grand Cayman (Wood and Sonoda 1973), St. Croix (Clavijo et al. 1980), and Flower Gardens off Texas (Bright and Cashman 1974). Earlier records are from less than 20 m, but it may be more common on shelf-edge reefs where fewer fish collections have been made.

SYNGNATHIDAE

Acentronura dendritica (Barbour 1905)
pipehorse

UPRM 3719 (1: 42), hand, 16 m, south of Media Luna reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, DL Ballantine, 5 Nov 1979.

This unusual pipefish is very distinctive as it looks like a cross between a seahorse and pipefish. One specimen was collected on rubble bottom of the algal plain off Media Luna reef, La Parguera. An additional specimen was photographed and collected in the La Parguera area, but could not be found in the museum collections (PLC). It is known from Bermuda (Smith-Vaniz et al. 1999), Bahamas, Hispaniola (Dawson 1982), and Colombia (Acero and Garzón 1988) in

the Caribbean. Formerly placed in the Atlantic genus *Amphelikturus* Dawson (1985) relegated it to a subgenus of the more widespread Indo-Pacific genus *Acentronura*.

TRIGLIDAE

Prionotus ophryas Jordan & Swain 1885
bandtail searobin

ANSP 144673 [formerly UPRM 2603] (1: 80), dipnet, 8 m, sandy bottom, near pilings, Crashboat Basin, Aguadilla, Puerto Rico, JE Randall, 12 Jun 1965; UF 207073 (1: 101), trawl, 70 m, off Arecibo, Puerto Rico, OREGON Stat. 2668 (18° 31'N 66° 47.5'W), 8 Oct 1959.

The bandtail searobin primarily occurs at continental locations from the Dry Tortugas, Bay of Campeche and Venezuela (Ginsburg 1950, Ross, 1983, Cervigón, 1991). There are island records from the Bahamas (Böhlke and Chaplin 1968), Jamaica (Caldwell 1966), and St. Croix (Randall 1996). The form listed as *Prionotus grisescens* Teague from Jamaica is reported to be a synonym of *P. ophryas* (Miller and Richards 1991). Its rarity at island locations suggests it might be part of a waif fauna.

SERRANIDAE

Bullisichthys caribbaeus Rivas 1971
pugnose bass

Collected, diver, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, PL Colin; specimen lost.

This diminutive (<60 mm SL) pugnosed serranid with its distinctive dorsal spot is apparently quite common on the deep wall off the southwestern coast of Puerto Rico (PLC). One was collected and photographed in aquarium (Plate 1A). Previous submersible work reported it from only one dive south of St. John (Nelson and Appeldoorn 1985). Rivas (1971) described it from the Bahamas, Serrana Bank, Nicaragua, and Dominica. One additional specimen was reported from off Sombrero Island just east of the Virgin Islands (Smith and Erdman 1973). It is also common off Lee Stocking Island, Bahamas at 90-150 m (GDD, pers. obs.) suggesting it may still be unfamiliar to scientist in the region, thus

may be more common than indicated by the few reports in the literature.

Epinephelus niveatus (Valenciennes
in Cuvier & Valenciennes 1828)
snowy grouper

ANSP 144999 (1: 61), 15 m, rock on muddy bottom, off Río Añasco, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 1975; No collection (1), photograph, artificial reef site, 18.3 m, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, R Wallace; 1976; AMNH 36922 (1: 87), 2 nmi. NW of Buoy R6 off Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, R/V STAHL, 1 Dec 1977; UPRM 3675 (1: 123), quinaldine, 16.5 m, 1.5 nmi south of Laurel reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, JJ Kimmel, 20 Nov 1979.

The species has not been reported from the Caribbean except for the periphery along the north coast of Cuba, Bimini, Bahamas (Smith 1971), and Venezuela (Cervigón 1991). There is a single old record from Jamaica (Boulenger 1895), but extensive deep-water fishing since then has not taken the snowy grouper (Thompson and Munro 1983). The rarity of this species, that would easily show up in the commercial fishery catch, suggests that larvae find their way to Puerto Rico from adult populations in other areas, e.g., South America, where it is not uncommon (Cervigón 1991). The UPRM specimen was taken as a juvenile and maintained in aquarium over three years. We note that the occurrence of the UPRM specimen closely followed the passage of Hurricane David suggesting that it might have been transported by unusual oceanographic conditions. It is apparently replaced by *Epinephelus mystacinus* (Poey) that is common in commercial catches in deep waters around Caribbean islands (Brownell and Rainey 1971).

GRAMMATIDAE

Lipogramma roseum Gilbert in Robins &
Colin 1979
rosy basslet

ANSP 141376 (1: 48), shelf-edge reef, 27 m, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, Sep 1978.

Previously known only from the type species from Isla de Providencia in the

PLATE 1. A. *Bullisichthys caribbaeus* from off La Parguera in aquarium (photograph by PL Colin). B. Saber goby from off La Parguera (photograph by PL Colin).

western Caribbean (Robins and Colin 1979), the above specimen came up alive and was maintained in aquaria for about six months. It appears to be a rare species as no other specimens were found in the museum catalogs. The identity of this specimen is still uncertain (A. Gill, pers. comm., Natural History Museum, London), as it does not completely fit the description of the type specimen.

ECHENEIDAE

Ernest Lachner (USNM) was working on the distribution of diskfishes (Echeneidae), but did not have the opportunity to publish the data before his death. The records reported here are from specimens at the USNM that were part of his study.

Phtheichthys lineatus (Menzies 1791)
slender suckerfish

USNM 202067 (1: 96), on *Carcharhinus longimanus*? (Poey), longline, off NW corner of Puerto Rico, OREGON Stat. 5461 (18° 34'N, 67° 24.3'W), 6 Jun 1965; USNM 202076 (1: 57), on *Xiphias gladius*? Linnaeus, off SW corner of Puerto Rico, OREGON Stat. 5462 (17° 45'N, 67° 34'W), 7 Jun 1965.

A worldwide tropical species typically found on barracuda (*Sphyraena barracuda* Walbaum) two specimens taken from longline catch were examined in the USNM collection. While it can be found attached to buoys or free swimming (Strasburg 1959) there is some uncertainty as to the host for these specimens as more than one potential host was on the deck when the suckerfish were collected. It is also found on sea turtles, sharks, and porcupine fish (*Diodon* sp.) (Cressey and Lachner 1970). It can be confused with the *Echeneis* spp. but is more slender and has a short disc with only 10 lamellae.

Remora brachyptera (Lowe 1839)
pearlfish remora

USNM 202075 (1: 134), on *Xiphias gladius*, longline, off SW corner of Puerto Rico, OREGON Stat. 5462 (17° 45'N, 67° 34'W), 7 Jun 1965.

It is surprising that this worldwide species was not previously reported from

Puerto Rico, as the parasites of big gamefishes were described (Williams and Bunkley-Williams 1996) and there is a considerable swordfish fishery in the area. It is also, more rarely, found on sharks, barracuda, and molas (*Mola mola* Linnaeus and *Masturus lanceolatus* (Liénard)) (Cressey and Lachner 1970). There are two other congeners, *Remora osteochir* (Cuvier) and *Remora remora* (Linnaeus), in the area, the former reported from blue marlin (*Makaira nigricans* Lacepède) and dolphin (*Coryphaena hippurus* Linnaeus) and the latter from sharks. *Remora australis* (Bennett) found on whales and *Remorina albescens* (Temminck & Schlegel) found on manta rays are not reported from the area. Robins and Ray (1986) provides good figures and characters to differentiation of these species.

CARANGIDAE

Selene brownii (Cuvier 1816)
full moonfish

ANSP 23560-62 (3: 68-91 mm FL), Isabel Segunda, Puerto Rico, FISH HAWK; ANSP 151580 (1: 168 mm FL), seine, Sun Oil plant site, Bahía Yabucoa, Puerto Rico, Hixson et al., 20 Jan 1982; UPRM uncat. (1: 58 mm FL), Bahía Fosforescente, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, DD Trueblood, 25 Mar 1983; UPRM uncat. (2: 124-129 mm FL), trawl, 7 m, off Caño Corazones, Bahía Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, JE Ramsey, 18 Feb 1967; UPRM uncat. (2: 147-152 mm FL), trawl, 10 m, north shore, Bahía Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, JE Ramsey, 23 Sep 1966; UPRM uncat. (4: 50-61 mm FL), trawl, 11 m, Bahía Añasco, Puerto Rico, B Yoshioka, 14 Jul 1987; UPRM uncat. (1: 46 mm FL), trawl, 2.5 m, Bahía Añasco, Puerto Rico, B Yoshioka, 14 Jul 1987; UF 60252 (1: 170 mm FL), bridge, Boca de Cangrejos, Puerto Rico, AB Cochran, 22 Jan 1964.

Berry and Smith-Vaniz (1978) indicated that there were two short-finned *Selene* (formerly classified in the genus *Vomer*) species, *S. setapinnis* (Mitchill) and *S. spixii* (Swainson) in the Caribbean. *Selene spixii* is a junior synonym of *S. brownii* and we follow Eschmeyer et al. (1998) in assigning *brownii* to Cuvier (1816). *Selene brownii* and *S. setapinnis* can be differentiated by the

number of gill rakers and body depth that changes with increasing size. Body depth measurements used to differentiate the two are for specimens greater than 140 mm FL (Berry and Smith-Vaniz 1978). Most of our specimens are smaller, but had the low gill raker count and deep body of *S. brownii*. This species is common in Bahía Mayagüez (Ramsey 1967) from where there are an additional 26 lots with 284 individuals ranging from 25-156 mm FL in the URPM collection. None of the specimens examined so far can be attributed to *S. setapinnis*, thus its occurrence in Puerto Rico must be questioned.

SCIAENIDAE

Ophioscion punctatissimus Meek &
Hildebrand 1925
impostor drum

UPRM 461 (1: 105), trawl, 2 m, mud bottom, Bahía Añasco, Puerto Rico; ANSP 115620 (52: 30-108), seine, SW of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, Foster & Loos, 12 Jul 1969; ANSP 115573 (154: 27-115), seine, SSW of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, Foster & Loos, 13 Jul 1969; ANSP 115655 (27: 34-87), seine, E of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, Foster et al., 15 Jul 1969; ANSP 116706 (1: 110), seine, SW of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, Loos et al., 25 Jul 1969; ANSP 116721 (2: 105-118), seine, NE of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, JJ Loos, 25 Jul 1969; ANSP 116723 (1: 105), seine, SE of Río Guayanes mouth, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, Loos et al., 25 Jul 1969; ANSP 118660 (13: 32-110), seine, SSW of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, Foster & Loos, 20 Jan 1971; ANSP 118526 (1: 110), seine, Río Guayanes mouth, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, Cepeda Medina et al., 26 Jan 1971; ANSP 118697 (2: 70-116), rotenone, SW of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, Loos et al., 28 Jul 1971; ANSP 129978 (28: 54-117), seine, SW of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, JJ Loos, 25 Jul 1973; ANSP 132076 (1: 94), seine, Río Guayanes mouth, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, JJ Loos, 27 Jul 1973; ANSP 129947 (4: 58-84), seine, SSW of Playa de Guayanes,

Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, JJ Loos, 27 Jul 1973; ANSP 132027 (1: 104), seine, E of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, JJ Loos, 27 Jul 1973; ANSP 151463 (2: 44-46), seine, Punta Quebrada, Bahía Yabucá, Puerto Rico, Stacey et al., 2 Jul 1981.

This species is somewhat problematic as the congener *Ophioscion adustus* (Agassiz) is occasionally reported from Puerto Rico. Schultz (1945) indicates that specimens of *O. adustus* in Evermann and Marsh (1900) were actually *O. punctatissimus*. Chao (1978) could not place *O. adustus* based on the original description as the figure and text do not agree and there is no type specimen. He surmised that it might belong in another genus most likely *Micropogonias*. There were several specimens labeled as *O. adustus* in the UPRM collection that were re-identified as *Micropogonias furnieri* (Desmarest) upon closer examination. It seems evident that the minute chin barbels of *M. furnieri* are easily missed in some instances leading to an erroneous identification as *O. adustus*. The only *Ophioscion* species found in Puerto Rico is *O. punctatissimus* where it can be common, but not widespread. *Ophioscion punctatissimus* can be distinguished from *Micropogonias* and *Stellifer* by the lack of chin barbels, low dorsal-fin ray count (22-24), and chin pore pattern (five mental pores).

Sciaena trewavasae Chao & Miller 1975
Ethelwynn's drum

USNM 228255 (3: 157-165), baited fish trap, 146 m, off Río Grande de Arecibo mouth, Puerto Rico, 25 Aug 1977.

This species was previously reported from off Colombia and Venezuela where it was collected from 115-394 m (Chao and Miller 1975). The depth of collection here is the upper end of a fish trap line. The specimens may have actually been taken much deeper, as such, may be part of the slope fauna of the Puerto Rican Plateau.

Stellifer sp. A
alpha star drum

ANSP 116706 (1: 68), seine, SW of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucá, Puerto Rico, Loos et al., 25 Jul 1969.

Chao (1978) reported this still undescribed

species from Venezuela. Cervigón (1993) reported additional specimens from Venezuela, but none from outside of the area. This is the first island record of this species that is distinguished by the dark lining of the mouth. *Stellifer colonensis* Meek & Hildebrand and *S. stellifer* (Bloch) are also reported from Puerto Rico, though *S. stellifer* could not be confirmed by specimens (Dennis 2000). Table 1 lists the distinguishing characters of the Puerto Rican *Stellifer* species.

POMACENTRIDAE

Chromis scotti Emery 1968
purple reeffish

UPRM 3716 (1: 59), spear, rocky pinnacle, 47 m, off baseball park, Rincón, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 6 Feb 1976.

This species is not uncommon on the deep reef (>35 m) off La Parguera (PLC). None were reported from a submersible survey in 1985 (Nelson and Appeldoorn 1985). Originally thought to be a Florida endemic (Emery 1968) it is now known from the Gulf of Mexico, Bahamas, Belize, Jamaica, St. Croix, Colombia, and Curaçao (Colin 1974, Palacio, 1974, Hensley and Smith 1977, Clavijo et al. 1980). It is more abundant at continental locations suggesting that it has a Caribbean peripheral distribution. The single specimen we have is unique in having 14 dorsal-fin rays and a pale center to the caudal fin forming a "V" but otherwise matches the description of *scotti*.

POLYNEMIDAE

Polydactylus oligodon (Günther 1860)
little-scale threadfin

UPRM 3060 (1: 118), rotenone, <2 m, rocky shore, Yabucoa, Puerto Rico, Eger

TABLE 1. Characters that differentiate *Stellifer* species from the Puerto Rican Plateau

Character	<i>colonensis</i>	<i>stellifer</i>	Sp. A
Preopercular margin spines	two	three or four	four
Dorsal-fin rays	23-24	18-20	23-24
Total gill rakers	29-33	32-38	37-41
Mental pores	6	5	5
Mouth color	pale	pale	dark

et al.; ANSP 115599 (6: 32-68), seine, SSW of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucoa, Puerto Rico, Foster et al., 13 Jul 1969; ANSP 115633 (2: 50-94), seine, SW of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucoa, Puerto Rico, Foster & Loos, 12 Jul 1969; ANSP 115671 (17: 42-78), seine, E of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucoa, Puerto Rico, Foster & Loos, 15 Jul 1969; ANSP 118511 (1: 123), seine, SSW of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucoa, Puerto Rico, Foster & Loos, 26 Jan 1971; ANSP 129980 (1: 73), seine, Sun Oil Refinery Jetty, SW of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucoa, Puerto Rico, JJ Loos, 25 Jul 1973; ANSP 132028 (8: 38-64), E of Playa de Guayanes, Puerto Yabucoa, Puerto Rico, JJ Loos, 27 Jul 1973.

While *Polydactylus virginicus* (Linnaeus) is well documented from Puerto Rico no *P. oligodon* have been reported. Previously *P. oligodon* was considered a synonym of *P. virginicus*, but Randall (1966) showed that it is a valid species. It is known from south Florida, Jamaica, Isla de Mona (Dennis unpublished data), St. Croix (Clavijo et al. 1980), Colombia (Palacio 1974), Venezuela (Cervigón 1993), and Trinidad (Randall 1966). At Puerto Yabucoa where the above specimens were taken, both species occurred together in 6 of 13 collections. In the six collections where the two species overlapped *P. virginicus* outnumbered *P. oligodon* 143 to 35. Feltes (1986) has recently reviewed the systematics of the family and indicated that the most consistent character differentiating the two species is lateral line scales with *P. oligodon* having 68-74 and *P. virginicus* 53-62.

OPISTOGNATHIDAE

Opistognathus gilberti Böhlke 1967
yellow jawfish

ANSP 134240 (1: 42), 55 m, shelf-edge reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 28 Jan 1978; ANSP 138876 (1: 53), 54 m, shelf-edge reef, Salinas de Ensenada, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 28 Feb 1978.

The yellow jawfish was only previously reported from the Bahamas (Böhlke 1967) and St. Croix (Clavijo et al. 1980). It is found frequently deeper than 33 m over the

dropoff in sand patches from Salinas de Ensenada to La Parguera on the southwest coast of Puerto Rico (PLC). Thresher (1984: 130) included a photograph of Colin's from Puerto Rico. It was also collected at nearby Isla de Mona (Dennis unpublished data) and Roatan (PLC).

Opistognathus lonchurus Jordan &
Gilbert 1882
moustache jawfish

ANSP 142700 [formerly UPRM 2521] (1: 108), sand near reef, 14 m, El Negro, Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, JE Randall, 28 Apr 1965; ANSP 134237 (1: 96), 49 m, off baseball park, Rincón, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 6 Feb 1976; ANSP 138362 (1: 93), 52 m, off baseball park, Rincón, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, Feb 1976; ANSP 138138 (1: 86), 52 m, off baseball park, Rincón, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 24 Oct 1976; ANSP 140955 (5: 77-97), 50 m, off baseball park, Rincón, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 1976.

The moustache jawfish is known from the Gulf of Mexico, Florida Keys, Cuba, Haiti, and Colombia in the tropical Atlantic (Böhlke and Thomas 1961, Böhlke 1967, Palacio 1974, Dennis and Bright 1988). It is occasionally found off the west coast of Puerto Rico being found on steep sloping bottom in sediment patches among rock outcrops (PLC). None were seen off La Parguera in similar habitats.

CHAENOPSIDAE

Emblemaria piratula Ginsburg & Reid in
Ginsburg 1942
pirate blenny

UPRM 3742 (2: 15.0-18.0), rotenone, 19.8 m, moat at shelf-edge reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, Kimmel et al., 11 Nov 1980; UF 208311 (1: 17.5), rotenone, 10.7 m, coral rubble, point at east end of great Salt Pond Bay, St. John, JE Randall, 29 Apr 1959; UF 214975 (2: 16.5-17.0), rotenone, 12.2 m, off Yawzi Point, St. John, Chess & McFarlane, 11 Oct 1959; ANSP 136248 (5: 12.3-17.5), 21 m, shelf-edge reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, Sep 1976.

This is another species thought to have a continental distribution. Greenfield and

Johnson (1981) reported one specimen from Belize with this provisional identification and noted the significant range extension. Most specimens are from deeper than 12 m, which may account for the limited number of specimens taken to date.

Emblemariopsis bottomei Stephens 1961
shorthead blenny

UPRM 3745 (1: 21.2), rotenone, 3.7 m, live *A. palmata* branch, Turrumote, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, GD Dennis, 28 May 1986; UPRM uncat. (2: 19.1-21.0), rotenone, 3.7 m, dead *A. palmata* frond, Turrumote, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, GD Dennis, 28 May 1986; UPRM uncat. (6: 19.4-22.8), quinaldine, 3 m, Laurel reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, Eger & Prentice, 20 Jun 1973.

During a trip in search of hole dwelling *Acanthemblemaria* three individuals of the shorthead blenny were found in living colonies of *Acorpora palmata* (Lamarck), two from a dead frond and one from a hole in living coral. Acero (1984) synonymized *Emblemariopsis* with *Coralliozetus* based on small size and sexually dimorphic coloration. There appears no good justification for the synonymy, as neither is a uniquely derived character. We retain the genus *Emblemariopsis* here. Acero (1984) also synonymized *E. bottomei* with *Emblemariopsis bahamensis* Stephens without explanation. The specimens reported here all exhibit the distinctively shorter head length of *E. bottomei* and there was no overlap in this character or sexual dimorphism. This species is previously known only from the type locality, Los Roques, Venezuela (Stephens 1970), though *E. bahamensis* was reported from Culebra (Humann 1994) and St. Croix (Clavijo et al. 1980). There are two specimens of the shorthead blenny reported from Isla de Mona (Dennis unpublished data).

Emblemariopsis occidentalis Stephens 1970
blackfin blenny

ANSP 176583 [formerly UPRM uncat.] (1: 11.9), quinaldine, 19.8 m, shelf-edge reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, JJ Kimmel, 16 Mar 1982.

This specimen was close to *Emblemariop-*

sis signifera (Ginsburg), but possessed orbital cirri and lacked black spots. Pigmentation is very similar to Figure 5 of Stephens (1970). The blackfin blenny is differentiated from the recently described *Emblemariopsis ruetzleri* (Tyler & Tyler) by possessing only 13 pectoral-fin rays (Tyler and Tyler 1997). It was previously reported from the Bahamas, Grand Cayman, Martinique, Grenadines, and Isla Providencia (Stephens 1970, Smith-Vaniz and Böhlke 1991).

Lucyablennius zingaro (Böhlke 1957)
arrow blenny

UPRM 2314 (1: 25), rotenone, 54.9 m, shelf-edge reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, JE Randall, 14 Nov 1964; UPRM 3287 (1: 29), quinaldine, 9.2 m, Mario reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, Waldner & Williams, 30 Mar 1976; ANSP 144655 [formerly UPRM 2586] (2: 20-22), rotenone, *Ocyurus chrysurus* stomach, El Negro reef, Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, JE Randall, 1 Jul 1965.

The arrow blenny is reported from Bahamas, Belize, Honduras, Panamá, and Colombia (Böhlke and Chaplin 1968, Greenfield 1972, Palacio 1974, Acero and Garzón 1985) and Caribbean records from Jamaica (Colin and Gomon 1973, Colin 1974) and St. Croix (Clavijo et al. 1980). Greenfield and Johnson (1981) reported this as a deep-water species, though one of our specimens was taken inshore at Mario reef. Lack of previous records may be due to its deep-water nature.

Stathmonotus hemphillii Bean 1885
blackbelly blenny

UMMZ 171165 (1: 22), causeway, San Geronimo and Condado rocks, San Juan, Puerto Rico, Michhan & Smith, 10 Oct 1955.

Hastings and Springer (1994) reviewed the genus and reported this species from Haiti and St. Croix, but not from any Puerto Rican Plateau location. Usually it is found in shallow water associated with corals (Böhlke and Chaplin 1968, Greenfield and Johnson 1981). Here it was taken on a rocky shore almost intertidally. Hastings and Springer (1994) moved the genus *Stathmonotus* from the family Labrisomidae to Chaenopsidae.

LABRISOMIDAE

Labrisomus filamentosus Springer 1960
quillfin blenny

ANSP 144386 (1: 115), 18 m, reef slope, Congo Cay, St. John, M. Dowgiallo, 3 May 1977.

This is one of two deep-water *Labrisomus*. It is rare throughout its range where it is found in the Bahamas, Grand Turk Island, Hispaniola, Barbados, and the outer shelf of Honduras and Nicaragua (Springer and Rosenblatt 1965, Emery and LaBelle 1981, Smith-Vaniz and Böhlke 1991).

Starksia atlantica Longley 1934
spotback blenny

UPRM 3161 (1: 12.3), rotenone, 8 m, Horseshoe reef, Anegada, Prentice et al., 8 Mar 1973.

This is a shallow-water species known from the Bahamas, islands off Central and South America, Jamaica (Colin 1971), Hispaniola, St. Croix (Clavijo et al. 1980) and Antigua (Greenfield and Johnson 1981). Only one specimen from Anegada at the far northeastern end of the Puerto Rican Plateau was found in collections. In addition, four specimens are reported from Isla de Mona (Dennis unpubl. data).

Starksia smithwanizi Williams & Mounts 2003
brokenbar blenny

UPRM uncat. (5: 10.0-18.0), rotenone, 4.6 m, forereef, Turrumote, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, J Rodriguez, 2 May 1986; UPRM uncat. (2: 12.0-15.5), rotenone, 4.6 m, fore-reef, El Palo, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, Hensley et al., 18 Mar 1986.

The recently described brokenbar blenny replaces the closely related *Starksia fasciata* (Longley) in the Antilles. It is a strictly island species found at Navassa Island, St. Croix, Antigua, and Dominica (Gilbert 1965, Clavijo et al. 1980, Williams and Mounts 2003). Here specimens were taken on the mid-shelf reefs at shallow depths.

GOBIIDAE

New genus, new species
saber goby

ANSP 150387 (2: 22.2-26.1), 91 m, shelf edge, S of Margarita reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, May 1978.

This beautiful goby has yet to be described though it was previously reported as the "filamentous goby" by Colin (1974). It is also found off the southwestern coast of Puerto Rico (PLC) (Plate 1B) and forms large aggregations on the wall at 90-150 m off Lee Stocking Island, Bahamas (Dennis pers. obs.) and Glovers Reef, Belize (Colin 1974). This species were tentatively identified as *Bollmannia* based on the large eye and scales (26-28 in lateral series), but J. Van Tassell (pers. comm., Hofstra University) indicates that it will be placed in an Indo-Pacific genus. Preserved specimens can be identified by the elongate dorsal spines that reach the caudal fin and light bands on the caudal fin that represent gold bands in live specimens.

Bollmannia communis Ginsburg 1942
ragged goby

ANSP 147645 (3: 43-49), Margarita reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, May 1978; UPRM 1557 (1: 41), dredge, 37 m, mud bottom, Añasco, Puerto Rico, Randall et al., 29 Mar 1963; UPRM 2196 (1: 39), trawl, off Añasco, Puerto Rico, JE Randall, 7 Aug 1964; UPRM uncat. (2: 45-48), trawl, 26 m, off Río Añasco, Puerto Rico, B Yoshioka, 11 Aug 1987.

Several *Bollmannia* specimens were collected in Puerto Rico, but their specific identification was difficult to determine due to poor species descriptions in the literature. The genus is in need of revision. There are only two species known from Caribbean islands, *Bollmannia boqueronensis* Evermann & Marsh and *Bollmannia litura* Ginsburg. Our specimens are definitely not *B. boqueronensis* that is morphologically quite distinct. They have a body pattern similar to *B. litura*, but dorsal- and pectoral-fin ray counts are too high. Meristic counts (dorsal VII, 14; anal 14; pectoral rays 21-23) agree best with *Bollmannia communis*,

known only from the Gulf of Mexico. Ginsburg (1942) compared *B. litura* to *B. communis* noting a larger eye in *B. litura* with no overlap in measurements. Also *B. litura* lacks a distinct first dorsal spot. Our specimens have slightly elongate dorsal-fin spines and dorsal-fin spots, thus closely resemble *B. communis* (Figure 2). Either fin-ray counts are more variable than previously reported or counts are consistent and dorsal spot and spine length are more variable. It is hard to definitively place them in either species as such we tentatively assign them to *B. communis*. As it is found on muddy bottom, it may be a species previously overlooked due to the lack of sampling in a rather unique and limited habitat on Caribbean islands.

Chriolepis fisheri Herre 1942
translucent goby

ANSP 145008 (1: 19.7), 21 m, edge of sand channel, shelf-edge reef, N of El Buoy, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 6 Oct 1976.

A diminutive species previously reported to only 18 mm SL, it is found in deep water along the shelf-edge dropoff. Additional specimens (not extant) were collected from sand tilefish (*Malacanthus plumieri* (Bloch)) burrow rubble at the shelf edge in La Parguera (PLC). It is reported from the Bahamas (Böhlke and Chaplin 1968) and Barbados (type locality). Museum databases contain additional records from Belize, Honduras, Haiti, and St. Barthélemy.

Ctenogobius stigmaturus (Goode & Bean 1882)
spottail goby

UF 106938 (2: 18.5-27.5), beach, west of Mosquito pier, Vieques, JS Coles, Aug 1960; UPRM 3721 (1: 23.5), night light, mud bottom, 1 m, mangrove lagoon, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, GD Dennis, 14 Sept 1988.

The spottail goby is rare on Caribbean islands. Gilbert and Randall (1979) listed this species as *Gobionellus stigmaturus* and limit it to southern Florida and Cuba. Museum databases indicate specimens from Bermuda, Belize, Panamá, and Guadeloupe. The specimen from La Parguera was

FIG. 2. A. *Bollmannia communis*, 40.5 mm SL, UPRM 1557. B. *Bollmannia communis*, 39.0 mm SL, UPRM 2196 (photographs by JE Randall).

taken on muddy bottom near red mangrove prop roots.

Elacatinus pallens (Ginsburg 1939)
semiscaled goby

UPRM 3720 (2: 10.2-11.0), quinaldine, 16.8 m, reef crest, shelf-edge reef, Salinas de Ensenada, Puerto Rico, JJ Kimmel, 30 Sep 1981; ANSP 149296 (1: 12.2), Margarita reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, May 1978.

The semiscaled goby is reported from the Bahamas, Grand Cayman, Hispaniola, Antigua, Grenadines, Belize, Albuquerque Cays, (Böhlke and Robins 1968), and Venezuela (Cervigón 1994). Our specimens are from greater than 15 m depth suggesting a deep-water preference, though it is found in shallower waters in the Bahamas (Böhlke and Chaplin 1968). Hoese (1971) placed the species under subgenera *Elacatinus* and *Tigrigobius* in Böhlke and Robins (1968) in

the genus *Elacatinus* and we follow this placement.

Elacatinus prochilos (Böhlke & Robins 1968)
white-striped goby

UPRM 3547 (2: 20.1-22.8), 4.6 m, El Negro reef, Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 5 Feb 1973.

A coral dwelling goby known to occur in Jamaica, St. Croix, Anguilla, St. Barthélémy, Antigua, Martinique, Grenadines, Barbados, Yucatán, and Belize (Böhlke and Robins 1968, Colin 1975). The above specimens fill in the gap between Jamaica and St. Croix. Apparently it is not common, but observed occasionally off the west coast of Puerto Rico (PLC).

Elacatinus tenox (Böhlke & Robins 1968)
slaty goby

UPRM uncat. [missing] (1), on sponge (*Neofibularia nolitangere*), 21 m, shelf-edge reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, PL Colin.

This sponge dwelling goby is only known from a few specimens taken in St. Croix (Clavijo et al. 1980), Dominica, Nevis, Isla de Aves, and Panamá (Colin 1975). It is found on the toxic sponge *Neofibularia nolitangere* (Duchassaing and Michelotti) in the shelf edge "moat" off La Parguera. The individuals from Isla de Aves were taken from the same sponge species.

Oxyurichthys stigmalocephalus (Mead & Böhlke 1958)
spottfin goby

ANSP 144379 (2: 57-58), 12.2 m, soft bottom, El Negro reef, Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, PL Colin, 5 Feb 1976; ANSP 144495 [formerly UPRM 2661] (1: 56), 12.2 m, sand and *Halophila* bottom, Crashboat Basin, Aguadilla, Puerto Rico, Randall & Cooke, 24 Jun 1965; UPRM 3723 (1: 82), quinaldine, sandy bottom, leeward side, Laurel reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico.

Mead and Böhlke (1958) described this species, as *Gobionellus stigmalocephalus*, from the Bahamas and Bay of Campeche. Gilbert and Randall (1979) examined specimens from Antigua and off Guyana and suggested it be placed in the genus *Oxyurichthys*. Pezold (1990) provided data supporting the placement of the species in *Oxyurichthys*. There are also museum database records from Belize and Martinique. It prefers sandy bottom.

Pycnomma roosevelti Ginsburg 1939
Roosevelt's goby

ANSP 149437 [formerly UPRM 2301] (1: 19.3), reef, La Parguera, Puerto Rico, PL Glynn, 12 Feb 1964.

This goby is previously known only from Isla de Providencia (Ginsburg 1939) and Jamaica (Caldwell 1966). There are museum database records from Honduras and Isla de San Andres. This species may be more common than the available records indicate, as its small size requires a fine mesh net and a keen eye to collect it, even during ichthyocide application (W. Smith-Vaniz, pers. comm., USGS).

ARIOMMATIDAE

Ariomma regulus (Poey 1868)
spotted driftfish

ANSP 157304 (4: 23.0-25.5), 1 m, White Bay, Guana Isl., Ford et al.

McKenney (1961) reported juveniles of this species from the Bahamas, Florida Keys, and north of Venezuela in the tropical western Atlantic. Additional juvenile specimens are reported from Colombia (Palacio 1974) and Venezuela (Cervigón 1994). Adults are bottom dwellers at depths of 100-500 m and juveniles pelagic up to 75 mm TL. Adults may be restricted to continental margins with juveniles found in the Caribbean expatriated from these populations. There is only one other ariommid known from the Caribbean, *Ariomma bonidi* Fowler, that can be differentiated from *A. regulus* by lack of spots on body and shallower body depth (<30% SL) (Haedrich and Horn 1969).

BOTHIDAE

Bothus robinsi Topp & Hoff (ex Jutare) 1972
spottail flounder

FSBC 1550 (1: 91), trawl, 49 m, N of Tortola, OREGON Stat. 2612 (18° 35'N, 64° 42.5'W), 27 Sep 1959; USNM 282698 (1: 107), trawl, 51 m, NW of St. Thomas, OREGON Stat. 2626 (18° 29'N, 65° 20'W), 29 Sep 1959.

The spottail flounder is reported from Bermuda (Smith-Vaniz et al. 1999), the Bahamas (Böhlke and Chaplin 1968), Florida (Topp and Hoff 1972), and Venezuela (Cervigón 1996). There are no records from any Antillean locations. Topp and Hoff (1972) reported this species as most abundant from 37-55 m in the eastern Gulf of Mexico. Local specimens were also taken in deeper water. *Bothus* can have a protracted larval stage suggesting it may be recruited from other areas.

ACHIRIDAE

Achirus declivis Chabanaud 1940
lost sole

ANSP 144392 [formerly UPRM 1350] (3: 28-36), Laguna Joyuda, Puerto Rico,

Randall et al., 26 Oct 1963; ANSP 143003 [formerly UPRM 1349] (1: 125), rotenone, Laguna Joyuda, Puerto Rico, 18 Feb 1956; ANSP 143002 (1: 137), 31 m, mud bottom, off Añasco, Puerto Rico, Randall & Lalave, 29 Mar 1963; ANSP 144385 (1: 88), trawl, 27 m, off Añasco, Puerto Rico, 24 Mar 1943; ANSP 144513 [formerly UPRM 469] (1: 122), Río Guanajibo, Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, JA Rivero, 15 Mar 1948; ANSP 144515 [formerly UPRM 2275] (1: 58), trawl, Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, Bane & Morena, 9 Feb 1963; ANSP 144520 (1: 45), Caño Corazones mouth, Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, V Biaggi, May 1952; ANSP 144514 (1: 126), Puerto Rico.

This species has only been reported once since its original description being resurrected by C.L. Hubbs in unpublished work (Greenfield and Thomerson 1997). Chabanaud (1940) described *A. declivis* as a subspecies of *Achirus achirus* (Linnaeus) from the Gulf of Paria between Trinidad and Venezuela. Cervigón (1985, 1996) who made a careful examination of the soles did not report it from Venezuela. Notes in the jars indicated that Hubbs identified the specimens above as *A. declivis*. This species has faint obscure markings like *A. achirus*, but with low dorsal-fin (<59) and anal-fin (<45) ray counts similar to *Achirus lineatus* (Linnaeus). *Achirus declivis* can be separated from the more common *A. lineatus* by the lack of spots on the caudal fin, a narrower caudal peduncle, and eyes closer together (Greenfield and Thomerson 1997). Its validity as a species awaits a comprehensive revision of the genus *Achirus*, but ichthyologists should be cognizant that two forms exist in Puerto Rico.

MOLIDAE

Ranzania laevis (Pennant 1776)
slender mola

UPRM 3693 (1: 625 mm TL), washed up on beach, Río Guanajibo mouth, Mayagüez, Puerto Rico, Lugo & Rodriguez, 17 Jan 1989.

Robins (1968) reviewed the limited data on this species from the western Atlantic. The only other records from the Caribbean

are from Martinique (Pellegrin, 1912) and Venezuela (Cervigón 1996). Our specimen, of similar size to Pellegrin's, is likely an adult, as the species does not exceed 800 mm TL (Fraser-Brunner 1951). This suggests that there might be a resident population in the Caribbean.

DISCUSSION

The lack of previous records for the species reported herein can be divided into three categories. The most common category is poorly sampled habitat in which falls the bulk of the records (33). Deep-water habitats (>20 m) are still not well known and 21 records can be attributed to this area. Twelve species are shallow-water inhabitants and most come from poorly sampled habitats, such as mangroves, soft bottom, or rocky shores. Species, such as *Sardinella janeiro*, *Anchoa cayorum*, *Selene brownii*, *Ophioscion punctatissimus*, *Stellifer* sp. A, *Polydactylus oligodon*, and *Achirus declivis* were not previously reported due to lack of taxonomic distinction from closely related species.

Most marine fishes disperse via planktonic larvae (Thresher 1984). Populations of marine fishes throughout the Caribbean are surprisingly homogeneous attesting to the dispersal ability of most taxa (Shulman and Bermingham 1995). Some taxa may be part of a waif fauna formed by expatriates from adult populations at other locations (Pielou 1979). Six species fall into this category. Four species, *Ariomma regulus*, *Epinephelus niveatus*, *Exocoetus obtusirostris*, *Prognichthys occidentalis*, were only taken as juveniles suggesting that local populations may not exist. The infrequent occurrence of the remaining two, adult *Bothus robinsi* and *Prionotus ophryas*, which occurred far outside their normal range, suggests an ephemeral existence on the Puerto Rican Plateau. A full account of the zoogeography of the marine fishes on the Puerto Rican Plateau is in preparation (Dennis 2000).

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